

BMF CP71: Examining the consequences of blockage, vandalism, and harassment for the climate cause

AISDL Team

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“[...] only by uniting the power of the entire village could they chase Snake away.”

—In “Virtue of Sacrifice”, *The Kingfisher Story Collection* [1]

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- What are the consequences of blockage, vandalism, and harassment activities for the cause of climate change mitigation?
- What kind of environmental activism leads to the escalation of violence?
- Which pathways (e.g., survival threats) do the activism lead to violence escalation?

The findings from this study are expected to provide insights into the effectiveness and appropriateness of strategies to raise public awareness and support and contribute to the societal transitions to address climate change [2-4].

1.2. Materials

The mindsponge theory will be used for conceptual development. Bayesian Mindsponge

Framework (BMF) analytics will be used for statistical analysis on a dataset of 89 blockage, vandalism, and harassment cases in 13 countries [5-8]. The Bayesvl R package, aided by the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm, will be employed for statistical analyses [7]. For more information on BMF analytics, portal users can refer to the following book [8]. For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/10778224> (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10778224).

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis indicates that rallies and demonstrations, marches, event disruption, and art vandalism are negatively associated with the probability of violence escalation. Meanwhile, road blockage and assault are positively associated with the probability of violence escalation, and sabotage has an ambiguous effect. (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Estimated coefficients

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps for registering to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institution email).
2. Provide your name, affiliation, and desired project role below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project is **Minh-Hoang Nguyen**.

AISDL members who have joined this project are Quan-Hoang Vuong and Viet-Phuong La.

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations [11], without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses [12].

References

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